

A Universal Turing Machine

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We reconstruct the didactic universal Turing machine by Marvin Minsky, MMo-UTM. We test it on a Turing machine interpreter coded in Lua, we comment on its limitations, and we enhance it twice: MMr-UTM, which can emulate any binary Turing machine; and MMc-UTM, which can emulate any Turing machine. The table of MMc-UTM is listed completely, with comments and an example of emulation. Since it has not any limitation and it uses a straightforward encoding, MMc-UTM makes a good constructive proof of the theorem of Turing completeness.

Keywords: Turing completeness, universal Turing machine

§1 Introduction

¶1 · Marvin Minsky (1967 §7) presented a UTM*, that is, a Universal Turing machine with a disclaimer. We will call it MMo-UTM. Disclaimer: MMo-UTM can only emulate Turing machines using two symbols, *blank* and another one, that work on a singly infinite tape, that is, MMo-UTM can only emulate binary and singly infinite Turing machines. In particular, MMo-UTM cannot emulate itself.

¶2 · We will discuss all MMo-UTM limitations and we will proceed to eliminate them, presenting two universal Turing machines in complete detail.

- Firstly, MMr-UTM, a revised version of MMo-UTM, which can emulate any binary Turing machine, but not itself.
- And finally, MMc-UTM, which can emulate any Turing machine, so it can emulate itself. MMc-UTM is a universal Turing machine without disclaimers.

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¶3 · In this paper, section §2, we firstly introduce the Turing machine. We start the section with an overview, in subsection §2.1, and a more detailed definition, in subsection §2.2. Then we will see some examples, in subsection §2.3, with the help of a Turing machine interpreter coded in Lua, which we have developed for testing. The section finishes, in subsection §2.4, defining *Turing completeness* and *universal Turing machine*.

¶4 · Next, in section §3, we reconstruct MMo-UTM. We start the section explaining its tape, in subsection §3.1, and, in subsection §3.2, we recreate the **diagram by Minsky that defines MMo-UTM**, from which we obtain its table, which is listed in full. Then, in subsection §3.3, we test it using the Turing machine interpreter. After doing some tests, we finish the section, in subsection §3.4, analyzing its limitations.

¶5 · Then, in section §4, we present its first enhancement, MMr-UTM, a Turing machine that can emulate any binary Turing machine. The first subsection, §4.1, describes its tape, compared with MMo-UTM's tape. Then, in subsection §4.2, we present its three new sub-machines, each one solving a limitation of MMo-UTM, the patch that transforms MMo-UTM into MMr-UTM, and the complete **diagram of MMr-UTM**. In subsection §4.3, we finish the section testing MMr-UTM.

¶6 · Section §5 is devoted to the theorem of binary Turing completeness, which states that there is a Turing machine that can emulate any binary Turing machine. MMr-UTM is a constructive proof of the theorem. This theorem together with another one by Shannon imply that there is a universal Turing machine.

¶7 · Therefore, in section §6, we present a universal Turing machine. Since it was designed on top of MMo-UTM and it completely eliminates its limitations, we call it MMc-UTM. We start the section explaining its tape, in subsection §6.1, and then, in subsection §6.2, we present the whole table and **diagram of MMc-UTM**, a comment about each of its sub-machines, and a complete example of MMc-UTM emulating a Turing machine. In subsection §6.3, we finish the section testing MMc-UTM.

¶8 · Section §7 is devoted to the theorem of Turing completeness, which says that there is a universal Turing machine, which is a Turing machine that can emulate any Turing machine. MMc-UTM is a constructive proof of the theorem.

¶9 · In section §8, we comment on the definition of universal Turing machine, and on the merit of an independent and concrete proof of the theorem of Turing completeness. The first universal computing machine was defined and designed by Turing, and its limitations are reviewed in subsection §8.1. Then, in subsection §8.2, we present the problem of encoding, raised by Davis and resolved by Minsky, who requires to encode program and data separately. In subsection §8.3, we explain that Minsky's separation requirement was the reason why Turing's original definition of universal Turing machine has been superseded. Finally, in subsection §8.4, we argue that the proof of the theorem of Turing completeness presented in this paper is foundational, because it is self-contained and constructive, since it presents a concrete Turing machine, MMc-UTM, which is universal without limitations and uses a straightforward encoding.

¶10 · We conclude, in section §9, with a short summary.

§2 Computing

§2.1 Turing machine

¶1 · The seminal reference of computing is its founding paper by [Turing \(1936\)](#), where he presents his *a*-machine, now known as Turing machine, which is his mathematical model for computing devices. A *Turing machine* is a tape controlled by a processor.

¶2 · The *tape* is read and write memory, and it is divided in squares, where each square can contain one symbol out of a finite set of symbols, or none. When a square contains no symbol, we say that it is *blank*. We will consider that *blank* is a symbol, though a *special* one. Each square has exactly one neighbor square to the left and one neighbor square to the right, meaning that the tape is infinite and that no computation will abort because of a lack of squares, though the number of non-*blank* squares will always be finite. Another way of seeing it is that the tape is finite but potentially infinite, and that new *blank* squares are created whenever either end of the tape is going to be overstepped.

¶3 · The *processor* is a finite-state automaton. Then, the processor is in each moment in exactly one state out of a finite set of states, and the next state and the output depend on the current state and the input. In the case of the Turing machine processor, the input is read from the scanned square of the tape, and the output is a pair composed of a symbol and a movement, where the symbol is written to the scanned square and the *movement* is *left* or *right*, so the next scanned square will be the neighbor one to the left, or the neighbor one to the right. So a *table* defining the next state and the pair of symbol to write and movement to do for each possible current state and read symbol determines completely the Turing machine behavior. We will say that the pair of current state (C) and read symbol (R) is the *index*, and that the triplet of next state (N), symbol to write (W) and movement to do (M) is its corresponding *instruction*. Together, the index with its corresponding instruction form a *quintuple*, which defines a *transition*. As the number of states and the number of symbols are both finite, the table is finite.

¶4 · The processor state, the tape content and the scanned square define the *situation* of the Turing machine. A *computation* starts from a well-defined situation and is executed in a loop with four stages —read, transition, write, and move— that is exited whenever the transition is a *halting* one, and then we say that the Turing machine has halted. We will assume without loss of generality that in the initial situation the state is the *initial state* and the scanned square is the leftmost non-*blank* square, if any, or another square to its left; if all squares are *blank*, then any one goes, as any one is as good as any other. From that initial situation, the Turing machine follows the instructions given in the table until the instruction to do is *halt*, thus ending the computation, or else it goes forever. Some more details and examples are provided below, in subsections §2.2 and §2.3.

¶5 · So the Turing machine transforms the string of symbols that was written on the tape when it started into the string of symbols that was written on the tape when it *halted*. From this point of view, each Turing machine implements a function from the set of strings of symbols to the set of strings of symbols, where the strings are finite in length and its symbols are drawn from a finite set. By definition, any function implemented by a Turing machine is a *computable function*. Note that not all these functions are total functions, because there is not any guarantee that a Turing machine on an initial string will *halt*, and then the function implemented by the Turing machine is not defined for those input strings on which the machine never *halts*.

§2.2 Processor

¶1 · A Turing machine \mathcal{P} processor has four main components: the states Φ , the symbols Γ , the movements Δ , and the table Π .

- The set of *states* Φ has to be finite, and the *initial* state, let us call it A , has to be in it, so $A \in \Phi$ and $|\Phi| \geq 1$.
- The set of ordinary symbols $\bar{\Gamma}$ has to be finite and not empty. The set of *symbols* Γ is set $\bar{\Gamma}$ plus the *blank* special symbol, let us write it 0 , that denotes that a tape square is blank. Then, $\Gamma = \bar{\Gamma} \cup \{0\}$, so $0 \in \Gamma$ and $|\Gamma| \geq 2$. We say that Γ is the *alphabet* to say that its symbols are totally ordered.
- The set of *movements* Δ has two elements: *left*, let us write it $<$; and *right*, let us write it $>$. Then, $\Delta = \{<, >\}$.
- The table Π is a total function $\Pi : \Phi \times \Gamma \rightarrow (\Phi \times \Gamma \times \Delta) \cup \{halt\}$, so it can be written as a table of $|\Phi| \times |\Gamma|$ rows and five columns, although we can omit some rows, as will we see soon. Table Π is also known as the *transition function*.

¶2 · Set Γ^* is the infinite set of the *finite* strings drawn from Γ . There is a practical problem regarding the *blank* special symbol, because there are two infinities of them on the tape, one to the left and the other to the right. We will ignore these two infinities, but we should be aware that a meaningful finite string of *blank* symbols concatenated with any of those two infinities could cause ambiguities.

¶3 · The default instruction is *halt*, which halts the Turing machine, so it does not change anything, neither the state nor the symbol, and it does not move. We could make explicit a *halt* instruction in the table by using, for example, $=$ to mean no movement, or we can rather omit the corresponding row.

¶4 · We use *meta-symbol* $*$ $\notin \Gamma$, to denote *any other symbol*. That is, index $C*$ applies when, in state C , the read symbol is any not explicitly defined. And, in that case, the corresponding instruction can also use a $*$, then meaning *the same symbol*, which is the read one. For example, if index $C1$ is not in the table, then row $C*B*<$ expands to $C1B1<$. Meta-symbol $*$ is handy when writing tables, but it can always be replaced by symbols; meta-symbol $*$ is just an abbreviation.

¶5 · We use *meta-string* $\infty \notin \Gamma^*$, to denote that a computation does not halt. With this notation, every Turing machine \mathcal{P} implements a function $\Gamma^* \rightarrow \Gamma^* \cup \{\infty\}$. Overloading the Turing machine name, for instance \mathcal{P} , which can refer to the Turing machine, to its processor, or to the implemented function, we will write $\mathcal{P}\langle\mathfrak{d}\rangle = \langle\mathfrak{r}\rangle$ to express that, when we write string $\mathfrak{d} \in \Gamma^*$ on the tape of Turing machine \mathcal{P} , it computes it and halts with the string $\mathfrak{r} \in \Gamma^*$ on the tape. So \mathfrak{d} is the input string to \mathcal{P} , and \mathfrak{r} is the corresponding output string. Should it no halt, we would write $\mathcal{P}\langle\mathfrak{d}\rangle = \infty$ instead.

¶6 · There are many versions of the Turing machine, and this is only one of them, basically the one by [Minsky \(1967\)](#). Some use quadruples instead of quintuples, so the instruction is a pair composed of the next state and the action, where the action can either be to write a symbol or to move. Others *halt* when reaching a halting state; we will use them frequently, since for us a *halting state* is any from which any transition is a halting transition. In other words, a halting state can be completely omitted from the *index*. Some others require two halting states, the accepting and the rejecting state, which we can also implement, and even more, since we are not limited to two halting states.

§2.3 Examples

¶1 · For example, this is the table for a Turing machine \mathcal{S}_2 that implements the successor function in base two without zero. In order to avoid ambiguities, we will not use the *blank* symbol to write the numbers, and then we will need a three-symbol alphabet; we will use alphabet $\Gamma = \{0, 1, 2\}$, so $|\Gamma| = 3$. We have added a header to help in reading each quintuple: C for the current state, R for the read symbol, N for the next state, W for the written symbol, and M for the movement. Four states and three symbols make a twelve-row table, but three are omitted because there are three halting transitions; in fact, state H is a halting state because all transitions from state H are halting ones.

\mathcal{S}_2	C	R	N	W	M
	A	0	A	0	>
	A	1	B	1	>
	A	2	B	2	>
	B	0	C	0	<
	B	1	B	1	>
	B	2	B	2	>
	C	0	H	1	<
	C	1	H	2	<
	C	2	C	1	<

¶2 · To see how this specific Turing machine \mathcal{S}_2 works, we can see what happens if we write the string 2212 on the tape, where the numeral 2212 in base two without zero is number twenty eight ($2 \cdot 2^3 + 2 \cdot 2^2 + 1 \cdot 2^1 + 2 \cdot 2^0$). That is, we will write the four symbols 2, 2, 1, and 2 from left to right in four consecutive squares. Then, the initial situation will be as follows.

0 0 0 A2 2 1 2 0 0 0

There are two infinities of *blanks*, one to the left and one to the right, which can be omitted, though we have kept three *blanks* on each side for didactic purposes. The scanned square is the one that has attached to it the current state, which is A at the start. Now, A2 is the index of the third row in the table, so the instruction to do is B2>, and therefore the next situation, after going to state B, rewriting the 2, and moving to the right, is as follows.

0 0 0 2 B2 1 2 0 0 0 For index B2, the instruction is also B2>.

0 0 0 2 2 B1 2 0 0 0 Now the index is B1, so the instruction is B1>.

0 0 0 2 2 1 B2 0 0 0 And, again, the instruction for index B2 is B2>.

0 0 0 2 2 1 2 B0 0 0 For B0, it is C0<, so the machine changes the state.

0 0 0 2 2 1 C2 0 0 0 And, for index C2, the instruction is C1<.

0 0 0 2 2 C1 1 0 0 0 Now, the instruction for C1 is H2<.

0 0 0 2 H2 2 1 0 0 0 Since index H2 is not in the table, the instruction to do is *halt*, so we have reached the final situation. Then the result of the computation, from which the two infinities of *blank* symbols are omitted, is the string 2221, which is twenty nine in base two without zero. We summarize it, thus: $\mathcal{S}_2\langle 2212 \rangle = \langle 2221 \rangle$. Defining *step* as a transition from a computing situation to the next one, this computation takes seven steps. Now you should try yourself $\mathcal{S}_2\langle 22 \rangle = \langle 111 \rangle$, and others.

¶3 · And, after having tried yourself some computations, you can verify whether you are doing it rightly or wrongly using the Turing machine interpreter in GitHub. Clone the repository github.com/ramoncasares/UTM, go to its dir `lua`, and execute the Lua interpreter in interactive mode, which uses `>` as prompt. Firstly, we will ask the interpreter to redo the previous computations.

```
...$ git clone git://github.com/ramoncasares/UTM.git
...$ cd UTM/lua/
.../UTM/lua$ lua -i
Lua 5.4.7 Copyright (C) 1994-2024 Lua.org, PUC-Rio
> mac = require("machine")
> TMS2t = "A0A0> A1B1> A2B2> B0C0< B1B1> B2B2> C0H1< C1H2< C2C1<"
> TMS2 = mac:new(TMS2t)
> TMS2:tape("2212")
2212
> TMS2:compute(true)
2221 |A2212|->|2B212|->|22B12|->|221B2|->|2212B0|->|221C20|->|22C110|->|2H2210|
> TMS2:tape("22")
22
> TMS2:compute(true)
111 |A22|->|2B2|->|22B0|->|2C20|->|C210|->|C0110|->|H01110|
```

And we can continue. Calling `compute` without arguments, it returns the tape and, instead of the steps, the number of steps. For more details on these and other functions, you can examine the source code, which is in directory `.../UTM/lua`.

```
> TMS2:compute()
112 5
> TMS2:compute()
121 6
> TMS2:compute()
122 5
> TMS2:compute()
211 7
> TMS2:compute()
212 5
> TMS2:compute()
221 6
> TMS2:compute()
222 5
> TMS2:compute()
1111 8
> TMS2:compute()
1112 6
> TMS2:compute()
1121 7
> os.exit()
```

¶4 · We could have saved some ink using the meta-symbol *. Both represent the very same table of Turing machine \mathcal{S}_2 , although the following one requires less typing.

C	R	N	W	M
A	0	A	0	>
A	*	B	*	>
B	0	C	0	<
B	*	B	*	>
C	0	H	1	<
C	1	H	2	<
C	2	C	1	<

¶5 · It is perhaps a bit easier for us to read this reduced form. It makes clearer that, when \mathcal{S}_2 is in state A, it will keep moving right while reading *blank* symbols, and that it will change to state B when it finds a non-*blank* symbol. This is the standard way to implement the convention that, in the initial situation, the scanned square is the leftmost one where a non-*blank* symbol is written, or any to its left. This convention makes convenient to interpret the state of the index of the first row of the table to be the *initial* state, the symbol of the index of the first row of the table to be the *blank* symbol, and the movement of the instruction of the first row of the table to be the *right* movement. Whenever possible, we will take advantage of this *first row rule*, by which the table contains all the information that defines a Turing machine.

¶6 · We can use the interpreter to verify that it is the same Turing machine.

```

.../UTM/lua$ lua -i
Lua 5.4.7 Copyright (C) 1994-2024 Lua.org, PUC-Rio
> mac = require("machine")
> TMS2xt = "AOAO>A*B*>BOC0<B*B*>COH1<C1H2<C2C1<"
> TMS2x = mac:new(TMS2xt)
> TMS2x:tape("2212")
2212
> TMS2x:compute(true)
2221 |A2212|->|2B212|->|22B12|->|221B2|->|2212B0|->|221C20|->|22C110|->|2H2210|
> TMS2x:tape("22")
22
> TMS2x:compute(true)
111 |A22|->|2B2|->|22B0|->|2C20|->|C210|->|C0110|->|H01110|
> TMS2x:compute()
112 5
> Ctrl-D

```

¶7 · Another simple Turing machine, which we will use later, is TM1022.

TM1022	C	R	N	W	M
	A	0	B	1	>
	A	1	A	1	<
	B	0	C	2	>
	B	1	H	0	<
	B	2	A	2	<
	C	0	B	2	<

This table of Turing machine TM1022 honors the first row rule, and then the *initial* state is A, *blank* is 0, and *right* is >.

¶8 · When we run TM1022 on an empty tape we get 1022, where we have omitted the infinities of blanks. We can verify it using the interpreter.

```
.../UTM/lua$ lua -i
Lua 5.4.7 Copyright (C) 1994-2024 Lua.org, PUC-Rio
> mac = require("machine")
> TM1022 = mac:new"A0B1> A1A1< B0C2> B1H0< B2A2< C0B2<"
> TM1022:compute(true)
1022   |A0|->|1B0|->|12C0|->|1B22|->|A122|->|A0122|->|1B122|->|H1022|
> os.exit()
```

All these examples and other ones are in file `test/machine.lua`, which is in directory `test`. To see them, you should go to `test`, set `LUA_PATH`, and read from `machine.lua`.

```
.../UTM/lua$ cd ../test/
.../UTM/test$ export LUA_PATH="../lua/?.lua"
.../UTM/test$ cat machine.lua - | lua -i
Lua 5.4.7 Copyright (C) 1994-2024 Lua.org, PUC-Rio
> -- test/machine.lua (RMCG20260116)
>
> mac = require("machine")
>
> -- TM1022 on an empty tape returns 1022
> TM1022 = mac:new"A0B1> A1A1< B0C2> B1H0< B2A2< C0B2<"
> TM1022:compute(true)
1022   |A0|->|1B0|->|12C0|->|1B22|->|A122|->|A0122|->|1B122|->|H1022|
> TM1022:compute(true)
10022  |A1022|->|A01022|->|1B1022|->|H10022|
> TM1022:compute(true)
100022 |A10022|->|A010022|->|1B10022|->|H100022|
.
.
.
> -- end test/machine.lua
> TM1022:compute(true)
1000022 |A100022|->|A0100022|->|1B100022|->|H1000022|
> TM1022:compute(true)
10000022 |A1000022|->|A01000022|->|1B1000022|->|H10000022|
```

¶9 · The set of states and the alphabet of Turing machine TM1022 are: $\Phi = \{A, B, C, H\}$ and $\Gamma = \{0, 1, 2\}$, meaning that, in fixed length binary, two bits are needed to encode the states and two bits are needed to encode the symbols. Applying the finite map

$$\{A \rightarrow 00, B \rightarrow 01, C \rightarrow 10, H \rightarrow 11; 0 \rightarrow 00, 1 \rightarrow 10, 2 \rightarrow 11; < \rightarrow 0, > \rightarrow 1\}$$

we get the binary encoded Turing machine TM1022b.

TM1022b	C	R	N	W	M
	00	00	01	10	1
	00	10	00	10	0
	01	00	10	11	1
	01	10	11	00	0
	01	11	00	11	0
	10	00	01	11	0

Running TM1022b on an empty tape we get 10 00 11 11, where we have omitted the infinities of blanks and each symbol is coded by two bits. Applying the map for the alphabet in reverse

$$\{0 \leftarrow 00, 1 \leftarrow 10, 2 \leftarrow 11\}$$

we get 1022, which is what TM1022 computed. We can verify it using the interpreter.

```
> code = require("code")
> TM1022b = code.tobinary(TM1022)
> TM1022b:tape("")
00
> TM1022b:compute({prest = "[", postst = "]"})
10 00 11 11      |[00] 00|->|10 [01] 00|->|10 11 [10] 00|->|10 [01] 11 11|->\
|[00] 10 11 11|->|[00] 00 10 11 11|->|10 [01] 10 11 11|->|[11] 10 00 11 11|
> Ctrl-D
```

§2.4 Turing completeness

¶1 · *Turing completeness* is a property of computing, namely, that *computing can express computing completely*. The original formulation is in Turing (1936), page 241, in the first sentence of section §6, titled *The universal computing machine*: “It is possible to invent a single machine which can be used to compute any computable sequence.”

¶2 · In modern terms, a *universal Turing machine* \mathcal{U} is a Turing machine that can emulate any Turing machine \mathcal{P} . The emulation has to be such that, if a computation by \mathcal{P} halts and computes a string, then the emulation by \mathcal{U} also halts and computes the same string, and if a computation by \mathcal{P} does not halt, then the emulation by \mathcal{U} does not halt either.

¶3 · Near the end of this paper, in §8, we will see why the modern formulation superseded the original one by Turing. But, before that, in order to understand Turing completeness better, we will see three universal Turing machines in complete detail. So, next, we will present and reconstruct the didactic universal Turing machine designed by Minsky (1967), §7. Here we will call it MMo-UTM.

§3 MMo-UTM

§3.1 Tape

¶1 · In order to emulate a binary Turing machine \mathcal{P}_2 , MMo-UTM uses the eight-symbol alphabet $\Gamma_o = \{0, 1, A, B, M, S, X, Y\}$, where 0 is the *blank* symbol. The initial tape only contains symbol M once, symbol Y twice, symbol X as many times as quintuples in \mathcal{P}_2 , symbol 1 a finite number of times, and any number of blanks, 0. MMo-UTM's tape has three areas:

- *tape*: leftly infinite emulated tape of \mathcal{P}_2 , where the symbol M marks the emulated scanned square;
- *index*: current/next state and read/write symbol of \mathcal{P}_2 ;
- *program*: description of \mathcal{P}_2 , that is, its table coded in fixed length binary, so each state is a different binary string of length s , and linearized, which is done by prefixing each quintuple with an X. The *blank* of \mathcal{P}_2 is coded 0, its other symbol is coded 1; *left* is coded 0, and *right* is coded 1.

¶2 · A valid initial tape is as follows, where value of the bit in the M square is the value of rightmost bit in the *index*, and the *initial* state is the one written in the *state* area of *index*.

$$0^* [01]^* M [01]^* Y [01]^{\{s\}} [01] (X [01]^{\{s\}} [01] [01]^{\{s\}} [01] [01])^+ Y 0^*$$

Our regular expressions use the following meta-symbols:

- postfix *, which means zero or more times;
- postfix +, which means one or more times;
- postfix ?, which means optional, that is, either once or none;
- postfix {n}, which means n times;
- the square brackets [and], which mean any of the symbols between them, so [01] means either 0 or 1 and [01]{s} stands for any binary string of length s, where s is the number of bits that encode each state of \mathcal{P}_2 ; and
- the parentheses (and), which enclose regular expressions.

§3.2 Table

¶1 · In the next page, you can find a recreation of Fig. 7.2-9, page 142, in Minsky (1967). We have named the states q_{mn} , where m is a sub-machine number, and n a state number. We use < for the left movement, instead of Minsky's L, and > for the right movement, instead of his R.

¶2 · This is the comma-separated values table of MMo-UTM, as read from the diagram.

```

./csv/MMo-UTM.csv
1  -- locate
2  q11,0,q11,A,<
3  q11,1,q11,B,<
4  q11,Y,q12,Y,>
5  q11,*,q11,*,<
6  q12,A,q13,0,>
7  q12,B,q14,1,>
8  q12,X,q21,X,>
9  q12,*,q12,*,>
10 q13,0,q15,A,<
11 q13,1,q16,B,>
12 q13,*,q13,*,>
13 q14,0,q16,A,>
14 q14,1,q15,B,<
15 q14,*,q14,*,>
16 q15,Y,q12,Y,>
17 q15,*,q15,*,<
18 q16,X,q11,X,<
19 q16,Y,q99,Y,>
20 q16,*,q16,*,>
21  -- copy
22 q21,0,q22,A,<
23 q21,1,q23,B,<
24 q21,*,q21,*,>
25 q22,Y,q24,Y,>
26 q22,*,q22,*,<
27 q23,Y,q25,Y,>
28 q23,*,q23,*,<
29 q24,0,q26,A,>
30 q24,1,q26,A,>
31 q24,X,q31,X,<
32 q24,*,q24,*,>
33 q25,0,q26,B,>
34 q25,1,q26,B,>
35 q25,X,q32,X,<
36 q25,*,q25,*,>
37 q26,X,q21,X,>
38 q26,*,q26,*,>
39  -- move
40 q31,M,q33,A,>
41 q31,*,q31,*,<
42 q32,M,q33,B,>
43 q32,*,q32,*,<
44 q33,A,q33,0,>
45 q33,B,q33,1,>
46 q33,X,q34,X,>
47 q33,*,q33,*,>
48 q34,0,q35,0,<
49 q34,1,q35,1,<
50 q34,*,q34,*,>
51 q35,0,q41,S,<
52 q35,1,q42,S,<
53 q35,A,q35,0,<
54 q35,B,q35,1,<
55 q35,*,q35,*,<
56  -- write and read
57 q41,A,q43,0,<
58 q41,B,q44,0,>
59 q41,*,q41,*,<
60 q42,A,q43,1,<
61 q42,B,q44,1,>
62 q42,*,q42,*,<
63 q43,0,q45,M,>
64 q43,1,q46,M,>
65 q43,*,q43,*,<
66 q44,0,q45,M,>
67 q44,1,q46,M,>
68 q44,*,q44,*,>
69 q45,S,q11,A,<
70 q45,*,q45,*,>
71 q46,S,q11,B,<
72 q46,*,q46,*,>
73  -- end

```

¶3 · MMo-UTM is a 8-symbol 24-state Turing machine. One of the 24 states is the halting state q99.

¶4 · This table does not obey the first row rule completely, so we have to specify that the *right* movement is >, and not the movement of the first row. Since, in the *index* of the first row, the state is the *initial* state q11, and the symbol is the *blank* symbol 0, these two do not need to be specified.

¶5 · Sub-machines Locate and Copy implement the *transition* stage of the computing loop, seen in §2.1. The other two sub-machines implement the other stages of the computing loop, but somehow mixed. Since the initial state is q11, then MMo-UTM starts when the *read* stage was already done.

§3.3 Testing

¶1 · Now, let us see MMo-UTM emulating TM101, which is a simple Turing machine that, when it starts on an empty tape, it halts with string 101 on the tape.

TM101	C	R	N	W	M
	A	0	B	1	>
	B	0	C	0	>
	C	0	H	1	<

These are the first commands of `test/MMo.lua`, a Lua session. Do not forget setting `LUA_PATH` when working from a different directory.

```

.../UTM/test$ export LUA_PATH="../lua/?.lua"
.../UTM/test$ lua -i < MMo.lua
Lua 5.4.7 Copyright (C) 1994-2024 Lua.org, PUC-Rio
> -- test/MMo.lua (RMCG20260409)
>
> mac = require("machine")
> MM = require("MM")
> test = require("test")
>
> -- The 101 machine
> TM101 = mac:new"A0B1> B0C0> C0H1<"
> TM101po = MM.TM2MMo(TM101)
> TM101:compute(true)
101    |A0|->|1B0|->|10C0|->|1H01|

```

As said, when TM101 starts on an empty tape, it computes string 101. We use function `MM.TM2MMo(tm)` to encode Turing machine `tm`, including its tape, into a string that makes a valid initial tape for MMo-UTM. So `TM101po` is the string that codes TM101 with an empty tape for MMo-UTM.

```

> MM.UTMo:tape(TM101po)
MY000X0000111X0101001X1001110Y
> MM.UTMo:steps(900)
1YA1SXM000111X0101001X1001110Y00000000[q45]0 900

```

Function `tm:steps(n)` runs Turing machine `tm` until it computes `n` steps or until it *halts*, and returns the situation and the number of steps executed. Notice that MMo-UTM will not *halt*, because in state `q45` and reading a 0 (*blank*), it will move to the right without changing the state. This happens because the emulation has stepped out the *tape* area. However, it works if we reserve two blank squares to the right of the scanned square.

```

> TM101xo = string.gsub(TM101po, "M", "M00")
> MM.UTMo:tape(TM101xo)
M00Y000X0000111X0101001X1001110Y
> MM.UTMo:compute()
1M1Y11AXAAAABBBXABABAABXBA01110Y 1103

```

Since the rightmost symbol in the *index* is an A, then the M should be interpreted to be a 0, and then the emulated *tape* is read 101.

¶2 · File `test/MMo.lua` also runs the example in [Minsky \(1967\)](#), §7.3, pages 143–144. The emulated Turing machine is called MM73. Below we show the situations selected by Minsky. For each situation we show the current state and the tape, where the scanned square is marked with a bar on top.

¶3 · The first seven lines reproduce the seven lines of the unnamed table in page 144, where the first line is the initial situation, and the seventh line is the situation after emulating one step. The seventh line and the following ones reproduce Table 7.3-1, in page 143, which shows the result after emulating some more steps.

```

q11      000M000Y01X̄00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q21      000M000Y01X̄AAAABXBAB110X10011X11100Y0
q33      000A0̄00YBBXAAAABXBABBAX10011X11100Y0
q35      000A000Y11XAAAABXBABBAX̄10011X11100Y0
q42      000A000Y1SX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q45      00M1̄000Y1SX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      00M1000Y1̄AX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      001M000Y0̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      00M1000Y1̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      0M01000Y1̄AX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      01M1000Y0̄AX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      010M000Y0̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      01M1000Y1̄AX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      011M000Y0̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      01M1000Y1̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      0M01000Y1̄BX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0
q11      M001000Y1̄AX00001X01110X10011X11100Y0

```

§3.4 Limitations

§3.4.1 Unidirectionality

¶1 · MMo-UTM only emulates Turing machines with singly left-infinite tapes, so it will fail to emulate computations that require more tape to the right than it is available, as seen when emulating TM101.

¶2 · Regarding unidirectionality, [Minsky \(1967\)](#) writes, §6.3.2 in page 129:

It can also be shown that Turing machines which have tapes infinite in both directions have no advantage or disadvantage over machines with singly infinite tapes.

He leaves the way of implementing universal Turing machines without this limitation as an exercise to the reader; it is problem 7.4-1. In the solution to that problem, which is in page 286, he makes two proposals:

- To *fold* the emulated tape, that is, to use the squares of the emulated tape alternatively so, for example, to emulate the squares to the left we use the odd ones and to emulate the squares to the right we use the even ones.
- To “replace the symbol M by a copy of the whole instruction region”. Then all the tape would be used but, instead of moving one symbol M, all symbols between the two symbols Y, including them, would have to be moved.

¶3 · His arguments are convincing, since they help us to see how it could be done, though they are complex to implement. Our solution will be easier: MMr-UTM will fulfill the requirement of bidirectionality by shifting all the *tape* when needed, see §4.2.3.

§3.4.2 Binariness

¶1 · The other important limitation of MMo-UTM is that it can only emulate binary Turing machines, which are those that use a two-symbol alphabet. Minsky (1967), §6.3 in page 129, using Shannon's binary theorem, see §5¶5, writes that

we can restrict our machines to the use of two symbols, without loss of generality.

In any case, since to eliminate this limitation requires more work, MMr-UTM will only emulate binary Turing machines, too. This limitation will be eliminated later on, when designing MMc-UTM, in §6.

§3.4.3 Dirtiness

¶1 · MMo-UTM output string is not clean, it has to be interpreted. For example, when emulating TM101 with enough *blanks* to the right, the output is:

1M1Y11AXAAAABBBXABABAABXBA01110Y,

which is read 101. Then the output should rather be 101, and we will design MMr-UTM with the requirement of cleanliness; see §4.2.2.

§3.4.4 Starting

¶1 · When MMo-UTM starts, the scanned square is the square where the leftmost symbol X is written. Since this is a peculiar requirement, in the Lua interpreter we had to implement a `resettape` function specific for MMo-UTM. Then, MMr-UTM will be designed to start from the leftmost non-*blank* symbol, or any to its left, which is the usual convention. Although this is not an important requirement, it is very easy to fulfill, just one additional state, see §4.2.1.

§3.4.5 Empty table

¶1 · Another minor limitation is that MMo-UTM fails to emulate the empty table Turing machine. The table is empty when all transitions are *halting* ones, so it corresponds to a Turing machine \mathcal{I} that does nothing: $\forall \mathfrak{d} \in \Gamma^* : \mathcal{I}\langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle = \langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle$. \mathcal{I} is also known as no-operation (NOP), and it implements the literal identity function. This is an edge case, which was probably overlooked by Minsky, that is very easy to overcome, since it does not require additional states, see §4.2.2.

§4 MMr-UTM

§4.1 Tape

¶1 · A peculiarity of MMo-UTM is that, after having read the symbol written in the scanned square of the *tape*, it overwrites it with an M, but taking care of saving its value in the rightmost square of the *index*. For this reason, when it starts, the value of the M square should be interpreted to be the value of the rightmost bit in the *index*. And it happens the same when it *halts*. Therefore, after *halting*, we have to interpret the value of M to be 0 or 1 depending on the value of the rightmost symbol of the *index* to be A or B. To simplify this, we have added another symbol to MMr-UTM, so the scanned square will be either N, for *one*, meaning that emulated scanned square is 1, or M, meaning that emulated scanned square is *blank*. With the additional symbol N, the alphabet of MMr-UTM is $\Gamma_r = \{0, 1, A, B, M, N, S, X, Y\}$, where 0 is the *blank* symbol.

¶2 · An additional requirement is that, whenever it halts, MMr-UTM will return the very same tape that the emulated binary Turing machine \mathcal{P}_2 computes. Therefore, before *halting*, MMr-UTM has to blank the *program* and *index*, and it has to tidy up the *tape*, which requires limiting it. To this end, MMr-UTM uses another symbol Y, the third one, to mark the leftmost position of the *tape* that has been reached. This leftmost Y on the *tape* is a *blank* for \mathcal{P}_2 , and it has to be the leftmost non-blank symbol on the tape of MMr-UTM, except temporarily while it is being moved to the left.

¶3 · A valid initial tape for MMr-UTM is as follows, where the regular expression uses the meta-symbols seen for MMo-UTM, see §3.1.

$$0^*Y[01]^*[MN][01]^*Y[01]\{s\}0(X([01]\{s\}[01][01]\{s\}[01][01])?)^+Y0^*$$

§4.2 Table

§4.2.1 Start

¶1 · Another peculiarity of MMo-UTM is that it does not start from the leftmost non-blank symbol, or from a blank at its left, a convention we follow, but it starts from the leftmost X on the tape, which is the X separating the *index* from the *program*. MMr-UTM resolves this problem by adding a new *initial* state q00: in state q00, it moves to the right until an X is found, and then it goes to state q11. These are the first lines of file MMr-UTM.csv.

../csv/MMr-UTM.csv

```

1 -- start
2 q00,0,q00,0,>
3 q00,X,q11,X,<
4 q00,*,q00,*,>

```


§4.2.2 Clean

¶1 · Since MMo-UTM *halts* when the whole *program* has been inspected without finding any instruction, then cleaning starts when, in state q16, the rightmost symbol Y is read. States q13 and q14 only read a Y when the *program* is just an X, that is, when all \mathcal{P}_2 transitions are halting ones, see §3.4.5. The cleaning task is simple: after state q16, or q13 or q14, has erased the rightmost Y, state q01 moves to the left blanking the *program* and the *index*, and then state q02 tidies up the *tape* and *halts* after erasing the leftmost Y. Having added the symbol N simplifies this task, since now the read symbol has not been overwritten.

```

5 -- clean
6 q01,Y,q02,0,<
7 q01,*,q01,0,<
8 q02,M,q02,0,<
9 q02,N,q02,1,<
10 q02,Y,q99,0,>
11 q02,*,q02,*,<
23 q13,Y,q01,0,<
27 q14,Y,q01,0,<
32 q16,Y,q01,0,<
    
```


§4.2.3 Shift

¶1 · Our last requirement for MMr-UTM is to avoid the singly infinite tape limitation of MMo-UTM. Minsky makes two proposals, see §3.4.1, but we will implement a simpler solution in MMr-UTM: to shift all the *tape* when needed. That is, when the emulated movement is going to intrude into the *index*, MMr-UTM will shift every written square on the *tape* one position to the left. This task also requires the use of the third symbol Y that marks the leftmost position of the *tape* that has been reached.

¶2 · In case the emulation tries to move onto the second Y, that is, if being MMr-UTM in state q44, it reads a Y, then it keeps moving to the left until finding the leftmost Y but remembering each bit to write it in the next to the left square. Firstly, state q51 writes the M and, depending on the symbol overwritten, it goes to state q52 or to state q53. State q52 remembers to have read a 0, and q53 to have read a 1. Finally, state q54 writes the new Y and, since it has read a *blank*, it goes to state q45. In case the emulation tries to move onto the first Y, that is, if being in state q43, MMr-UTM reads a symbol Y, then it overwrites it with an M, moves to the left and goes to state q54, which rewrites the Y.

```

78 q43,0,q45,M,>
82 q44,0,q45,M,>
90 -- shift
91 q51,0,q52,M,<
92 q51,1,q53,M,<
93 q51,*,q51,*,<
94 q52,1,q53,0,<
95 q52,Y,q54,0,<
96 q52,*,q52,*,<
97 q53,0,q52,1,<
98 q53,Y,q54,1,<
99 q53,*,q53,*,<
100 q54,0,q45,Y,>
101 q54,*,q54,*,<
    
```


§4.2.4 Patch

¶1 · And that is all. This is the patch that transforms `MMo-UTM.csv` into `MMr-UTM.csv`. It was produced this way: `diff MMo-UTM.csv MMr-UTM.csv > MMo2MMr.patch`.

```

./csv/MMo2MMr.patch
1 0a1,11
2 > -- start
3 > q00,0,q00,0,>
4 > q00,X,q11,X,<
5 > q00,*,q00,*,>
6 > -- clean
7 > q01,Y,q02,0,<
8 > q01,*,q01,0,<
9 > q02,M,q02,0,<
10 > q02,N,q02,1,<
11 > q02,Y,q99,0,>
12 > q02,*,q02,*,<
13 11a23
14 > q13,Y,q01,0,<
15 14a27
16 > q14,Y,q01,0,<
17 19c32
18 < q16,Y,q99,Y,>
19 ---
20 > q16,Y,q01,0,<
21 40a54
22 > q31,N,q33,A,>
23 42a57
24 > q32,N,q33,B,>
25 64c79,80
26 < q43,1,q46,M,>
27 ---
28 > q43,1,q46,N,>
29 > q43,Y,q54,M,<
30 67c83,84
31 < q44,1,q46,M,>
32 ---
33 > q44,1,q46,N,>
34 > q44,Y,q51,Y,<
35 72a90,101
36 > -- shift
37 > q51,0,q52,M,<
38 > q51,1,q53,M,<
39 > q51,*,q51,*,<
40 > q52,1,q53,0,<
41 > q52,Y,q54,0,<
42 > q52,*,q52,*,<
43 > q53,0,q52,1,<
44 > q53,Y,q54,1,<
45 > q53,*,q53,*,<
46 > q54,0,q45,Y,>
47 > q54,*,q54,*,<

```

¶2 · In the patch we can see the three sections that implement **Start**, **Clean**, and **Shift**, links to the new sections (going to states `q01`, `q54`, and `q51`), and then those that deal with symbol `N`. Compared with `MMo-UTM`, `MMr-UTM` uses one additional symbol (`N`) and seven states more (`q00–q02` and `q51–q54`).

¶3 · `MMr-UTM` is a 9-symbol 31-state Turing machine. One of the 31 states is the halting state `q99`. In the next page, you can find the complete diagram of `MMr-UTM`.

§4.3 Testing

¶1 · You can use the Turing machine interpreter to test `MMr-UTM`. It could be helpful to run

```

.../UTM/test$ export LUA_PATH="./lua/?.lua"
.../UTM/test$ lua -i < MMr.lua > MMr.out

```

and then examining the resulting file `.../UTM/test/MMr.out`.

¶2 · Similarly to `MMo-UTM`, function `MM.TM2MMr(tm)` encodes Turing machine `tm`, including its tape, into a string that makes a valid initial tape for `MMr-UTM`. And function `MM.MMr2TM(tp)` decodes string `tp`, a `MMr-UTM` tape, returning the corresponding Turing machine.

§5 Binary Turing completeness theorem

¶1 · Whenever it halts, MMr-UTM returns the very same binary string that the emulated binary Turing machine \mathcal{P}_2 computes. And, if \mathcal{P}_2 does not halt, then MMr-UTM will not halt, either. Therefore, MMr-UTM is a perfect emulator of binary Turing machines. The *theorem of binary Turing completeness* says:

THEOREM: *There is a binary-universal Turing machine.*

¶2 · PROOF: In other words,

$$\exists \mathcal{U}_2 \in \mathfrak{T}, \forall \mathcal{P}_2 \in \mathfrak{T}_2, \forall \mathfrak{d}_2 \in \Gamma_2^* : \mathcal{U}_2 \langle \mathfrak{p}_2 | \mathfrak{d}_2 \rangle = \mathcal{P}_2 \langle \mathfrak{d}_2 \rangle$$

where:

- \mathfrak{T} is the set of Turing machines, so \mathcal{U}_2 is a Turing machine,
 - \mathfrak{T}_2 is the set of binary Turing machines, which are those that use only two symbols, *blank*, coded 0, and another symbol, coded 1, so their alphabet is $\Gamma_2 = \{0, 1\}$, and then \mathcal{P}_2 is a binary Turing machine and \mathfrak{d}_2 is a binary string,
 - $\mathcal{P}_2 \langle \mathfrak{d}_2 \rangle \in \Gamma_2^*$ is the output string computed by \mathcal{P}_2 when its input is \mathfrak{d}_2 , or $\infty \notin \Gamma_2^*$ if it does not *halt*,
 - $\mathfrak{p}_2 \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}_2}$ is the program that encodes \mathcal{P}_2 in the language $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}_2}$ implemented by \mathcal{U}_2 , $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}_2} \subset \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}_2}^*$,
 - $\mathfrak{p}_2 | \mathfrak{d}_2 \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}_2}$ is the string that composes program \mathfrak{p}_2 and string \mathfrak{d}_2 , and
 - $\mathcal{U}_2 \langle \mathfrak{p}_2 | \mathfrak{d}_2 \rangle \in \Gamma_2^*$ is the corresponding output string computed by \mathcal{U}_2 , or $\infty \notin \Gamma_2^*$ if it does not *halt*.
- ¶3 · Since MMr-UTM, in the place of \mathcal{U}_2 , satisfies the equation, we have shown that the theorem is TRUE. ◊
- ¶4 · MMr-UTM is a constructive proof of the theorem. Notice that MMo-UTM does not satisfy the equation because of its unidirectionality, see §3.4.1, because of its dirtiness, see §3.4.3, and because it fails to emulate \mathcal{I} , see §3.4.5.
- ¶5 · The only remaining limitation of MMr-UTM is that the emulated Turing machine has to be binary, that is, it has to use only two symbols, *blank* and another one. Regarding this limitation Shannon (1956), page 163, wrote:

It is also possible, as we will now show, to construct a machine, C, which will act like any given Turing machine A and use only two symbols 1 and 0 on its tape, one of which, 0 say, is the symbol for a blank square.

Here, we will call it the *binary theorem* by Shannon.

¶6 · Following Shannon, to emulate an arbitrary m -symbol n -state Turing machine A with a universal Turing machine that only emulates two-symbol Turing machines, as MMr-UTM, we would have to compute the corresponding binary Turing machine C, which, by his calculations, has at most $3n2^w + n(2w - 7)$ states, where $w \in \mathbb{N}$ is such that $2^{w-1} < m \leq 2^w$. This way, we would be transferring complexity from the universal Turing machine to the encoding, see §8.

¶7 · Together, the binary Turing completeness theorem and Shannon's binary theorem show that there is a universal Turing machine. So next we will design MMc-UTM, a universal Turing machine, that is, one that can emulate any Turing machine, without exceptions. We will base MMc-UTM on MMr-UTM, which is MMo-UTM revised.

§6 MMc-UTM

§6.1 Tape

¶1 · In order to emulate any Turing machine \mathcal{P} , MMc-UTM uses the same encoding for programs and data as MMo-UTM, with minor differences, as follows. MMo-UTM requires a binary fixed-length encoding for the emulated states $\Phi_{\mathcal{P}}$, and MMc-UTM too. We are denoting the number of bits that encode an emulated state \mathbf{s} . MMo-UTM uses a binary fixed-length *index*, and MMc-UTM too, which thus requires a binary fixed-length encoding for the emulated alphabet $\Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}$. We will denote the number of bits that encode an emulated symbol \mathbf{w} . Another requirement is that the emulated blank is a string of *blanks*, that is, a string of \mathbf{w} symbols 0 of MMc-UTM. Additionally, in order to avoid ambiguities, all other emulated symbols should start with a 1, though this is not a requirement. Finally, MMo-UTM encodes emulated *left* as 0 and emulated *right* as 1, and MMc-UTM too.

¶2 · The initial tape of Misky’s MMo-UTM has exactly one M on the tape, marking the emulated scanned square. The initial tape of MMc-UTM has \mathbf{w} consecutive M or N symbols, where \mathbf{w} is the number of bits needed to encode each emulated symbol. Save for this, the tape of MMc-UTM is organized the same way that the tape of MMr-UTM, see §4.1. As MMr-UTM, compared with MMo-UTM, MMc-UTM uses an additional symbol N, so the alphabet of MMc-UTM is $\Gamma_{\mathcal{C}} = \{0, 1, A, B, M, N, S, X, Y\}$, where 0 is the *blank* symbol.

¶3 · The initial tape of MMc-UTM contains symbol Y three times, \mathbf{w} times in total symbols M and N, symbol X as many times as quintuples in \mathcal{P} , and at least one, symbol 1 a finite number of times, and any number of blanks, 0. The initial tape of MMc-UTM is any described by the regular expression

$$0^*Y[01]^*[MN]\{\mathbf{w}\}[01]^*Y[01]\{\mathbf{s}\}[01]\{\mathbf{w}\}(X([01]\{\mathbf{s}\}[01]\{\mathbf{w}\}[01]\{\mathbf{s}\}[01]\{\mathbf{w}\}[01])^*)?+Y0^*$$

which uses the meta-symbols seen for MMo-UTM, see §3.1.

¶4 · The tape of MMc-UTM has three areas:

- *tape*: emulated tape of \mathcal{P} , where the consecutive symbols M and N mark the emulated scanned square and represent its value, M for 0 and N for 1;
- *index*: current/next state (*st*) and read/write symbol (*sy*) of \mathcal{P} ;
- *program*: description of \mathcal{P} , that is, its linearized table encoded in fixed length binary, done by prefixing each binary encoded quintuple of \mathcal{P} with a symbol X.

¶5 · We will follow the emulation of Turing machine TM1022b, see §2.3¶9, by MMc-UTM. The initial tape for our TM1022b example is shown below, where the scanned square is marked with a bar on top, which is, initially, the leftmost non-blank square:

YMMY0000X000001101X001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2 Table

§6.2.0 Start

¶1 · The initial situation of our TM1022b example is:

q00 YMMY0000X000001101X001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

¶2 · This first sub-machine, which we take from MMr-UTM, see §4.2.1, only uses one state, the *initial* state q00, which moves to the right until the leftmost X is found. Once the proper square is pointed to, it goes to state q11 to locate the instruction, see §6.2.1. So these are the first lines of file MMc-UTM.csv.

../csv/MMc-UTM.csv

```
1 -- start
2 q00,0,q00,0,>
3 q00,X,q11,X,<
4 q00,*,q00,*,>
```


¶3 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, the situation is as follows.

q11 YMMY0000X000001101X001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2.1 Locate

¶1 · We take the locate sub-machine of MMo-UTM. As Minsky (1967), page 139, explains:

It first searches to the right to find the first state-symbol pair that matches the one represented in the [index] area. On the path to the desired pair, it changes all 0's and 1's to A's and B's. After finding the desired pair, and changing it also to A's and B's, it runs back to the leftmost X.

¶2 · If an instruction is found, then it goes to state q21 to copy the instruction from the program into the index, see §6.2.2. If no instruction is found, then it goes to state q01 to finish, see §6.2.7; as done also for MMr-UTM, see §4.2.2, we have added two transitions to state q01, one from q13 and the other from q14, in order to deal with empty tables.

```
12 -- locate
13 q11,0,q11,A,<
14 q11,1,q11,B,<
15 q11,Y,q12,Y,>
16 q11,*,q11,*,<
17 q12,A,q13,0,>
18 q12,B,q14,1,>
19 q12,X,q21,X,>
20 q12,*,q12,*,>
21 q13,0,q15,A,<
22 q13,1,q16,B,>
23 q13,Y,q01,0,<
24 q13,*,q13,*,>
25 q14,0,q16,A,>
26 q14,1,q15,B,<
27 q14,Y,q01,0,<
28 q14,*,q14,*,>
29 q15,Y,q12,Y,>
30 q15,*,q15,*,<
31 q16,X,q11,X,<
32 q16,Y,q01,0,<
33 q16,*,q16,*,>
```


¶3 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, the situation is as follows.

q21 YMMY0000X̄AAA01101X001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2.2 Copy

¶1 · We take without any modification the copy sub-machine of MMo-UTM. As Minsky (1967), pages 139 and 140, explains:

It starts on the leftmost X, and from there shifts to the right until it has gone past the last A or B and sees for the first time some some 0's or 1's. These 0's or 1's describe the new state of [P], the new symbol which must eventually be printed in location M[N], and the direction of motion. Next the machine copies the 0's and 1's representing the [new state] and [new symbol] into the [index] region; it does not print [the direction of motion] but just remembers it.

¶2 · It copies the instruction from the *program* to the *index*, both the next state and the symbol to write. State q21 moves to the right till the leftmost unread bit in the *program*, and if its a 0 then it changes it to A and goes to state q22, but if its a 1 then it changes it to B and goes to state q23. State q22 (and q23) moves to the left until the middle Y, and then changes to state q24 (to q25). State q24 (and q25) moves to the right till the leftmost unwritten bit in the *index*, it changes it to A (to B), and goes to state q26. State q26 moves to the leftmost X, which marks the beginning of the *program*, and goes to state q21 to copy the next bit. If in state q24 (or q25) there are not any unwritten bit in the *index*, then it is the movement, so it goes to state q31 to emulate the left movement (or to q35 to emulate the right movement), see §6.2.3.

```

34 -- copy
35 q21,0,q22,A,<
36 q21,1,q23,B,<
37 q21,*,q21,*,>
38 q22,Y,q24,Y,>
39 q22,*,q22,*,<
40 q23,Y,q25,Y,>
41 q23,*,q23,*,<
42 q24,0,q26,A,>
43 q24,1,q26,A,>
44 q24,X,q31,X,<
45 q24,*,q24,*,>
46 q25,0,q26,B,>
47 q25,1,q26,B,>
48 q25,X,q35,X,<
49 q25,*,q25,*,>
50 q26,X,q21,X,>
51 q26,*,q26,*,>
    
```


¶3 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, since the movement is *right*, the situation is as follows.

```

q35      YMMYABBAXAAAAABBABX001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y
    
```

§6.2.3 Move

¶1 · It changes as many 0's or 1's to A's and B's as there are M's and N's. This way later, when reading, these marked bits will be found among all the 0's and 1's on the *tape*. In the process, the M's and N's are changed to S's.

¶2 · Let us see first the movement to the left. In this case, the A's and B's are written to the left of the M's and N's by state q32. But firstly, state q31 has moved from the *program*, where a left movement was read, through the *index*, until the rightmost M or N on the *tape*, and then another square to the left. If state q32 finds a Y, then the inspected *tape* has to be enlarged to the left, which is done by state q34. State q33 determines whether to go back to q32 to continue marking, or go forward to state q51, or to q52, to write, see §6.2.5.

```

52 -- move left
53 q31,M,q32,S,<
54 q31,N,q32,S,<
55 q31,*,q31,*,<
56 q32,0,q33,A,>
57 q32,1,q33,B,>
58 q32,Y,q34,A,<
59 q32,*,q32,*,<
60 q33,0,q51,0,>
61 q33,1,q51,1,>
62 q33,M,q32,S,<
63 q33,N,q32,S,<
64 q33,Y,q52,Y,<
65 q33,*,q33,*,>
66 q34,0,q33,Y,>
67 q34,*,q34,*,<
    
```


¶3 · Lets now see the movement to the right. In this case, the A's and B's are written to the right of the M's and N's by state q36. But firstly, state q35 has moved from the *program*, where a right movement was read, through the *index*, until the rightmost M or N on the *tape*. Then state q36 marks the bits to be read, but, if it finds the Y separating the *tape* from the *index*, then it goes to state q41 to make room, see §6.2.4. Finally, state q37 determines whether to go back to q36 to continue marking, or go forward to state q51 to write, see §6.2.5.

```

68 -- move right
69 q35,M,q36,S,>
70 q35,N,q36,S,>
71 q35,*,q35,*,<
72 q36,0,q37,A,<
73 q36,1,q37,B,<
74 q36,Y,q41,Y,<
75 q36,*,q36,*,>
76 q37,0,q51,0,>
77 q37,1,q51,1,>
78 q37,M,q36,S,>
79 q37,N,q36,S,>
80 q37,Y,q51,Y,>
81 q37,*,q37,*,<
    
```


¶4 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, since the movement was *right* and it finds a Y, the situation is as follows.

q41 YMSYABBAXAAAAABBABX001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2.4 Shift

¶1 · If trying to move to the right, it finds the middle Y, that is, if the emulation is trying to intrude into the *index*, then it has to make room for the symbol, so it will shift all the symbols on the tape. Conceptually, it is part of the right movement; it comes from state q36 when there is no room, and goes back to the state q37 to complete the movement. Though it has many transitions, is simple. States q41–q46 do the main shifting, each one remembering the symbol read, A, B, M, S, 0 or 1. State q47 writes the leftmost Y one square to the left, and state q48 moves to the leftmost S and goes back to state q37 to complete the movement, see §6.2.3.

```

82 -- shift
83 q41,B,q42,A,<
84 q41,M,q43,A,<
85 q41,N,q43,A,<
86 q41,S,q44,A,<
87 q41,*,q41,*,<
88 q42,A,q41,B,<
89 q42,M,q43,B,<
90 q42,N,q43,B,<
91 q42,S,q44,B,<
92 q42,*,q42,*,<
93 q43,0,q45,M,<
94 q43,1,q46,M,<
95 q43,N,q43,M,<
96 q43,S,q44,M,<
97 q43,Y,q47,M,<
98 q43,*,q43,*,<
99 q44,0,q45,S,<
100 q44,1,q46,S,<
101 q44,M,q43,S,<
102 q44,N,q43,S,<
103 q44,Y,q47,S,<
104 q44,*,q44,*,<
105 q45,1,q46,0,<
106 q45,Y,q47,0,<
107 q45,*,q45,*,<
108 q46,0,q45,1,<
109 q46,Y,q47,1,<
110 q46,*,q46,*,<
111 q47,0,q48,Y,>
112 q47,*,q47,*,<
113 q48,S,q37,S,<
114 q48,*,q48,*,>
    
```


- ¶2 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, the situation is as follows.
q37 YMSAYABBAXAAAAABBABX001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y
- ¶3 · And when the first right movement is completed, the situation is as follows.
q51 YSSAAYABBAXAAAAABBABX001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2.5 Write

¶1 · Every symbol *S* in the *tape* is overwritten with the symbol that is in the *index*. State *q51* moves to the *Y* that separates the *tape* from the *index*, and state *q52* moves to the rightmost *S*, and changes it to an *M*. Then state *q53* moves to the *X* that separates the *index* from the *program*, and state *q54* moves to the rightmost *A* or *B*, which overwrites with an *S*, and it remembers it going to state *q55* or *q56*. States *q55* and *q56* move to the *M* and overwrites it accordingly, that is, *q55* with a 0 and *q56* with a 1. Then, state *q57* inspects the square at its left; if it is a *S*, it overwrites it with an *M* and goes to *q53* to write another bit; otherwise it goes to state *q61* to read the symbol, see §6.2.6.

```

115 -- write
116 q51,Y,q52,Y,<
117 q51,*,q51,*,>
118 q52,S,q53,M,>
119 q52,*,q52,*,<
120 q53,X,q54,X,<
121 q53,*,q53,*,>
122 q54,A,q55,S,<
123 q54,B,q56,S,<
124 q54,*,q54,*,<
125 q55,M,q57,0,<
126 q55,*,q55,*,<
127 q56,M,q57,1,<
128 q56,*,q56,*,<
129 q57,0,q61,0,>
130 q57,1,q61,1,>
131 q57,A,q61,A,>
132 q57,B,q61,B,>
133 q57,S,q53,M,>
134 q57,Y,q61,Y,>
135 q57,*,q57,*,<
    
```


¶2 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, the situation is as follows.

q61 Y10AAYABSSXAAAAABBABX001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y

§6.2.6 Read

¶1 · The bits marked on the *tape* are written in the symbol part of the *index*. State q61 moves to the middle Y. State q62 moves right through the index and program restoring every A to 0 and every B to 1 until finding the first 0 or 1, or the rightmost Y. State q63 moves to the rightmost S that overwrites with an X and goes to state q64. State q64 moves to the rightmost A or B, and remembers it going to state q65 or to q66. State q65 then moves to the X and overwrites it with a 0; and state q66 with a 1. Both go back to q63 to read another bit. However, if in state q63 there is not any remaining S, the reading task is completed, the emulated step finishes, and MMc-UTM goes back to the initial state q00, see §6.2.0.

```

136 -- read
137 q61,Y,q62,Y,>
138 q61,*,q61,*,>
139 q62,0,q63,0,<
140 q62,1,q63,1,<
141 q62,A,q62,0,>
142 q62,B,q62,1,>
143 q62,Y,q63,Y,<
144 q62,*,q62,*,>
145 q63,S,q64,X,<
146 q63,Y,q00,Y,>
147 q63,*,q63,*,<
148 q64,A,q65,M,>
149 q64,B,q66,N,>
150 q64,*,q64,*,<
151 q65,X,q63,0,<
152 q65,*,q65,*,>
153 q66,X,q63,1,<
154 q66,*,q66,*,>
    
```


¶2 · When this sub-machine terminates the first time, the first emulated step is completed, and the situation is as follows.

```

q00      Y10MMY0̄100X000001101X001000100X010010111X011011000X011100110X100001110Y
    
```

This is a valid initial situation, save for the scanned square, which is not the leftmost Y.

§7 Turing completeness theorem

¶1 · Whenever it halts, MMc-UTM returns, simply encoded, the same string that the emulated Turing machine \mathcal{P} computes. And, if \mathcal{P} does not halt, then MMc-UTM will not halt, either. Therefore, MMc-UTM is a perfect emulator of Turing machines. The *theorem of Turing completeness* says:

THEOREM: *There is a universal Turing machine.*

¶2 · PROOF: In other words,

$$\exists \mathcal{U} \in \mathfrak{T}, \forall \mathcal{P} \in \mathfrak{T}, \forall \mathfrak{d} \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^* : \overleftarrow{\mathcal{U}\langle \mathfrak{p} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}} \rangle} = \mathcal{P}\langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle ,$$

where

- \mathfrak{T} is the set of Turing machines, so \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{P} are Turing machines,
 - \mathfrak{d} is an input string to \mathcal{P} ,
 - $\mathcal{P}\langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^*$ is the corresponding output string, or $\infty \notin \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^*$ if it does not halt,
 - the right pointing arrow hat represents encoding, so $\vec{\mathfrak{d}} \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$ is the string \mathfrak{d} encoded in the language $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$ implemented by \mathcal{U} , $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}} \subset \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$,
 - $\mathfrak{p} \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$ is the *program* that codes \mathcal{P} in the language $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$, so $\mathfrak{p} = \vec{\mathcal{P}}$,
 - the $|$ represents the composing operation of language $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$, so $\mathfrak{p} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}} \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$,
 - $\mathcal{U}\langle \mathfrak{p} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}} \rangle \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$ is the corresponding output string computed by \mathcal{U} , or $\infty \notin \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ if it does not halt, and
 - the left pointing arrow on top denotes the corresponding decoding, $\forall \mathfrak{d} \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^* : \overleftarrow{\vec{\mathfrak{d}}} = \mathfrak{d}$, which leaves ∞ unchanged, $\overleftarrow{\infty} = \infty$.
- ¶3 · Since MMc-UTM, in the place of \mathcal{U} , satisfies the equation, then we have shown that the theorem is TRUE. \diamond
- ¶4 · Therefore, MMc-UTM proves constructively the theorem of Turing completeness, and MMc-UTM is a universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} .
- ¶5 · It seems imposible that a complex Turing machine can be emulated by a simpler universal Turing machine. However, this is the case. MMc-UTM is a 9-symbol 44-state Turing machine that is universal, and then, even if \mathcal{P} is a γ -symbol ϕ -state Turing machine such that $\gamma > 9$ and $\phi > 44$, it can be emulated by MMc-UTM.

§8 Discussion

§8.1 Turing

¶1 · The first universal computing machine was designed by Alan Turing (1936), §7, who presented a UTM*, which we will call ATo-UTM. In his words (page 241), ATo-UTM “can be used to compute any computable sequence”, because his aim was to compute the binary expansion of any computable number, which is one that a Turing machine can calculate with arbitrary precision. Since mathematically the binary expansion is as valid as any other, the binary limitation was not a limitation for Turing. In other words, sometimes encoding can be abstracted away.

¶2 · The requirement of arbitrary precision means that, whenever a bit of the computable number that is being calculated is committed, it will not be recalculated anymore. Then, for Turing, it was enough to compute *sequences*, for which a singly infinite tape suffices. Thus, basically, ATo-UTM has the same limitations that MMo-UTM has, as seen in §3.4: unidirectionality, binarity, and dirtiness. For details on ATo-UTM limitations, see Petzold (2008), page 161.

¶3 · Even though ATo-UTM and MMo-UTM have the same limitations, ATo-UTM is much more complex than MMo-UTM. The reason, we can guess, is that ATo-UTM was the very first one, while MMo-UTM had the advantage of examining all previous trials. The reader interested on ATo-UTM will find Davies (2004) explanation clearer than the original exposition by Turing, for the same reason. By the way, ATo-UTM is so complex that Davies, although his aim was just to correct the errors, had to redesign ATo-UTM in order to run it. Following our naming practice, we should call the version revised by Davies ATr-UTM.

§8.2 Encoding

¶1 · Sometimes encoding can be abstracted away, but some other times encoding could be abused. This problem was addressed by Davis (1956), page 167.

The universality of a Turing machine is manifested by its ability, via a suitable encoding, to perform any computation which could be performed by any given Turing machine. However, the condition must surely be added that the encoding itself be, in some suitable sense, simple. For there would not be much point in claiming universality for a Turing machine for which the encoding would require, in essence, another universal machine to carry it out. This raises the problem of explicitly defining universal Turing machine, which problem is the subject of the present note.

Then, following Turing, a universal Turing machine is a Turing machine that can perform any computation. And, in addition, Davis requires (page 169) “that the encoding [of the computation] may be entirely accomplished by Turing machines which are not themselves universal.”

¶2 · Minsky (1967), whole first paragraph of §14.8.1 in page 277, goes further. In order to make “sure that the machine was not applied to the data during the encoding process”, he requires that “*the encodings for the machine structure and for the data [to be] done separately.*” This is why, in the equation of Turing completeness, see §7, program \mathbf{p} is Turing machine \mathcal{P} encoded and argument $\vec{\mathbf{d}}$ is data \mathbf{d} encoded *separately*, which are then composed, denoted by $|$. We will call Minsky’s requirement the *separation requirement*.

¶3 · Minsky made those comments because he had designed a 4-symbol 7-state Turing machine that can emulate any 2-tag system. Then, using a theorem by Cocke, presented in page 270, that affirms that, for any Turing machine \mathcal{P} , there is a 2-tag system that behaves like \mathcal{P} , he concludes that his 4-7-machine must be universal, though the encoding is not straightforward. As he writes, in page 278, “the conversion [doing the encoding] is a primitive-recursive operation [thus fulfilling Davis’ requirement]. In fact, it involves only writing down sixteen productions for each quintuple.” On the other hand, Minsky’s didactic encoding used by MMo-UTM is straightforward, just a finite mapping, see §3. And so they are MMr-UTM and MMc-UTM encodings, see §4 and §6.

¶4 · Minsky is right writing, again in page 277, that “there is not particular virtue in the quintuple formulation, and one might be able to get a simpler universal Turing machine with some other representation.” This has allowed him, and others following his track, to design small universal Turing machines but, by requiring an additional theorem, these universal Turing machines do not make self-contained proofs of the theorem of Turing completeness.

§8.3 Definition

¶1 · Our definition of universal Turing machine is not anymore the one by Turing (UTM*). The current definition of universal Turing machine (UTM) derives from the separation requirement by Minsky.

- Turing: a UTM* is a Turing machine that can perform any computation.
- Minsky: a UTM is a Turing machine that can emulate any Turing machine.

Neither ATo-UTM nor MMo-UTM qualify as universal Turing machines under the current definition, since neither can emulate itself. On the other hand, any universal Turing machine under the current definition can perform any computation, and then it “can be used to compute any computable sequence”, and then it is also universal by Turing’s definition. In summary, every UTM is a UTM*, but not the converse.

¶2 · Minsky’s separation requirement is the reason why the current definition of universal Turing machine has superseded the original one by Turing. Let us see it.

¶3 · Any computation can be performed in many ways. Let us take, for example, the computation that calculates the hundredth bit of the binary expansion of number π . There are several algorithms to calculate it, and for each algorithm several Turing machines that implement it, and then, at least, one way of encoding each Turing machine as a program for each universal Turing machine. Since number π is computable, our computation example is a halting one, so it will take a finite number of steps and it will scan a finite number of tape squares. Then, a singly infinite tape is enough, meaning that there are programs that compute it on a singly infinite tape. In summary, we can compute it using a UTM* that only emulates singly infinite tapes, but, since not every program goes, we have to make some judgements on the behavior of programs. For example, since MMo-UTM’s *tape* is *only* infinite to the left, we have to determine in advance how many squares to the right does each program require. And this is undecidable, given the halting problem and its consequences, in this case [Rice’s \(1953\) theorem](#).

¶4 · The current definition of universal Turing machine avoids this problem. And, in the case of MMc-UTM, which satisfies the current definition, encoding simply applies a finite mapping to translate each element (state, symbol or movement) in the Turing machine table into a binary string, so it is independent of its behavior; all is syntax, no semantics are involved.

§8.4 Foundations

¶1 · In order to compare our proof of the theorem, in sections §6 and §7, with others, it could be instructive to divert ourselves for a moment to the theory of recursive functions. In a very precise sense, recursion theory and computing theory are the same, since Turing (1937) proved that every recursive function is computable, and the converse. In that sense, the theorem of Turing completeness of computing is equivalent to the normal form theorem of recursion. However, Kleene (1952) presents his normal form theorem in page 288, using Gödel numbers and dense mathematical tools. Of course, it can be done in less pages; Davis (1958), who also uses recursion theory and Gödel numbers, presents the theorem of Turing completeness in page 64 and Kleene normal form theorem in page 171.

¶2 · In stark contrast to those proofs, the proof in this paper should be easy to follow, since the universal Turing machine presented, MMc-UTM, is completely defined, so it can be run in any Turing machine interpreter, and it is composed of eight sub-machines, each one with a specific task accomplished with eight states, or less. Once you understand how each sub-machine works, then it will also be easy to see how the whole machine works. At that point, you will convince yourself that there is a universal Turing machine. Surely, if you design your own universal Turing machine, which I encourage you to do, you will feel more assured, but even in that case you can elaborate on this one, MMc-UTM, to design yours, as I did on the universal Turing machine by Minsky (1967), MMo-UTM. In the end, the purpose of any mathematical proof should be to convince its reader that the theorem is TRUE.

¶3 · The advantage of Turing (1936) computing compared with other equivalent forms, such as recursion or lambda-calculus, is its conceptual simplicity. For example, it is documented, see Davis (1982), that, for stating what is effectively calculable, Gödel disregarded his own recursion and Church's lambda-calculus, and that he was instead convinced that Turing computing was the definitive answer only after he had read Turing's analysis, which is axiomatic, see Shagrir (2006). Using an analogy, Turing computing is machine code, while all other equivalent formulations are higher level languages.

¶4 · Then, an advantage of the proof in this paper is that, being of the lowest level, it does not need any abstraction. Another advantage is that, neither depending on other theorems nor on equivalences with other formulations, it is self-contained. And together, concreteness and independency, show the foundational character of the proof of the theorem of Turing completeness given in this paper, sections §6 and §7.

§9 Conclusion

¶1 · In this paper, we have presented the whole table of a universal Turing machine that has not any limitation, that is conceptually simple, and that uses a straightforward encoding. These are qualities that make it a good foundational and constructive proof of the theorem of Turing completeness.

Definitions

- alphabet* (§2.2¶1) completely ordered set of symbols, Γ
- binary theorem* (§5¶5) every Turing machine can be emulated by a two-symbol one
- binary Turing completeness theorem* (§5) there is a Turing machine that can emulate any two-symbol Turing machine
- blank* (§2.1¶2) empty tape square and its corresponding symbol
- computable function* (§2.1¶5) one implemented by a Turing machine
- computation* (§2.1¶4) from the initial situation, follow instructions till *halt*, if ever
- first row rule* (§2.3¶5) the first row declares the *initial* state, the *blank* symbol and the *right* movement
- halt* (§2.1¶4) instruction that terminates a computation
- halting state* (§2.2¶6) one from which all transitions are halting ones
- index* (§2.1¶3) instruction reference: current state, read symbol
- initial state* (§2.1¶4) state when starting a computation
- instruction* (§2.1¶3) what to do: either next state, write symbol and movement or *halt*
- meta-string* ∞ (§2.2¶5) a computation that does not *halt*
- meta-symbol* $*$ (§2.2¶4) any other symbol in index, and the same symbol in instruction
- MMc-UTM* (§6) universal Turing machine based on MMo-UTM, [see diagram](#)
- MMo-UTM* (§3) didactic universal Turing machine by Minsky, [see diagram](#)
- MMr-UTM* (§4) MMo-UTM revised, [see diagram](#)
- movement* (§2.1¶3) next scanned square, either *left* or *right*
- movements* (§2.2¶1) set of movements, $\Delta = \{left, right\}$
- processor* (§2.1¶3) a finite-state automaton
- program* (§7¶2) an encoded Turing machine, $\mathbf{p} = \vec{\mathcal{P}}$
- quintuple* (§2.1¶3) index and instruction defining a transition
- separation requirement* (§8.2¶2) program and data have to be encoded separately
- situation* (§2.1¶4) current state, tape content and scanned square
- states* (§2.2¶1) processor's set of states, Φ
- step* (§2.3¶2) transition from a computing situation to the next one
- symbols* (§2.2¶1) tape's set of symbols, Γ , or alphabet
- table* (§2.1¶3) transition function or what to do in every possible situation, Π
- tape* (§2.1¶2) inexhaustible chain of read and write squares
- transition* (§2.1¶3) a computing step definition or what to do in a specific situation
- transition function* (§2.2¶1) total function $\Pi : \Phi \times \Gamma \rightarrow (\Phi \times \Gamma \times \Delta) \cup \{halt\}$
- Turing completeness* (§2.4) computing can express computing completely
- Turing completeness theorem* (§7) there is a universal Turing machine
- Turing machine* (§2.1) a tape controlled by a processor, \mathcal{P}
- universal Turing machine* (§2.4¶2) a Turing machine \mathcal{U} that can emulate any Turing machine

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